

Investigation on recent deep learning- based molecular docking tools

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Abstract

Recently, deep learning technology has been applied on molecular docking, an important field for drug discovery and development. It is worthwhile to illustrate the mechanism and to give some usage profile of such new fancy deep learning-based molecular docking tools to the biomedical research community. Therefore, I chose 4 recent deep learning-based molecular docking tools: EquiDock, EquiBind, DiffDock, DiffDock-L to be investigated. Firstly, I drew schematic diagrams and tried to write easily understandable description to illustrate the main mechanism of these 4 tools. Briefly speaking, EquiDock uses attention mechanism to find key-points, EquiBind introduces conformation fine-tuning for small molecule ligand, DiffDock performs forward and reverse diffusion processes, and DiffDock-L applies the scaling law to improve accuracy. Next, I submitted the computational job on the DiffDock-L webserver for PDB entry 6w70, and locally ran EquiBind and DiffDock-L for PDB entry 1a0q. The primary results showed that DiffDock-L's predicted ligand pose was much closer to the true ligand. Additionally, I carefully collected 10 new data samples from PDB website, then ran EquiBind and DiffDock-L on them, calculated RMSD value between predicted ligand pose and true ligand structure. Surprisingly, DiffDock-L can produce different ligand poses located in several chains of a dimer protein although some RMSD value looked strangely large, while EquiBind can only produce one ligand pose located in the first chain of a dimer protein. In conclusion, prediction accuracy of DiffDock-L was better than EquiBind, and DiffDock-L can produce more comprehensive ligand poses for dimer proteins, but when tested on very new data samples, such data driven methods cannot show very satisfactory performance so far.

Introduction

In this introduction section, I will introduce three aspects of background knowledge: molecular docking, deep learning technology and recent research events. And then, I will give the overview of the research project in this report.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking is a computational simulation for how a molecule is binding to another molecule. In most cases, researchers focus on using molecular docking to predict how a small molecule (ligand or substrate) is binding to a protein (receptor or enzyme), because this is important for drug discovery and development [1]. But protein-protein interaction simulation is also worthwhile for helping illustrate the molecular mechanism in biological activities. The core steps of traditional docking tools are searching conformational poses' space, scoring these poses by energetic function, ranking the poses by score values, then choosing the top N poses. Also, there are other operation steps in real practice (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Practical workflow of traditional and recent deep learning based-molecular docking

Left green boxes show the distinct aspects of traditional molecular docking. Middle black boxes show the common aspects of both types of molecular docking. Right blue boxes show the distinct aspects of recent deep learning based molecular docking. Dash line boxes indicate that these practical steps are optional.

Deep learning technology

Deep learning or neural network technology is a data driven method that, through multiple iterations of training by a large dataset on a pre-set architecture model, captures the inner features of the dataset, and obtain the understating of the dataset by fixing a set of parameters of the model. It has become popular since 2012 [2,3], firstly in computer science fields such as computer vision, natural language processing, and graph neural network representation learning. And very soon it has been spread to many other fields globally.

Recent research events

In recent years, deep learning technology has heavily surprised ordinary people at least by two well-known events. One was that in 2022 ChatGPT 3.5 was released and it can smartly chat with human in text form [4]. And the basic deep learning model of it is transformer with attention mechanism. This is in part why the full name of ChatGPT is “Generative Pre-trained Transformer for Chatting”. Another event was that in 2024 SORA was released and it can generate nearly perfectly matching short video under the human prompt [5]. And the key technique used in SORA is the generative diffusion model. Due to the powerful performance of such deep learning technology, the attention mechanism and diffusion model have been applied on vast fields in the past a few years. And the four recent molecular docking tools investigated in this research project (Table 1) also contain such technology. Specifically, EquiDock [6] and EquiBind [7] use attention mechanism to generate the key points of ligand and receptor, DiffDock [8] and DiffDock-L [9] use diffusion model to apply reverse diffusion process on unbound ligand to transform into the bound state. More explanation will be in the result section of this report.

Table 1. Release information about 4 recent deep learning-based molecular tools

Bold fonts indicate the authors occurring in the development for all these tools.

Release Date	Title of Article	Version of Article	Software	Authors
2021/11/15	Independent SE(3)-Equivariant Models for End-to-End Rigid Protein Docking	Version 1		Octavian-Eugen Ganea, Xinyuan Huang,
2022/03/15		Version 2	EquiDock	Charlotte Bunne, Yatao Bian, Regina Barzilay , Tommi Jaakkola , Andreas Krause
2022/02/07	EquiBind: Geometric Deep Learning for Drug Binding Structure Prediction	Version 1		
2022/03/17		Version 2	EquiBind	Hannes Stärk, Octavian-Eugen Ganea, Lagnajit Pattanaik, Regina Barzilay , Tommi Jaakkola
2022/05/19		Version 3		
2022/06/04		Version 4		
2022/10/04	DiffDock: Diffusion Steps, Twists, and Turns for Molecular Docking	Version 1		Gabriele Corso, Hannes Stärk, Bowen Jing,
2023/02/11		Version 2	DiffDock	Regina Barzilay , Tommi Jaakkola
	Deep Confident Steps to New Pockets: Strategies for Docking Generalization	Version 1	DiffDock-L	Gabriele Corso, Arthur Deng, Benjamin Fry, Nicholas Polizzi, Regina Barzilay , Tommi Jaakkola

Overview of this research project

It is worthwhile to illustrate the mechanism and to give some usage profile of such new fancy deep learning-based molecular docking tools to the biomedical research community. And I hope this project may help facilitate biomedical researchers' work and trigger new thoughts for improving such tools. Therefore, I chose the 4 recent deep learning-based molecular docking tools mentioned above to be investigated: EquiDock, EquiBind, DiffDock, DiffDock-L. The release information about them is in

Table 1. Basically, there are two main aspects of the content in this research project: theoretical mechanism investigation and computational practice exploration. For mechanism part, I drew schematic diagrams and tried to write easily understandable description to illustrate the main mechanism of these 4 tools. For practice part, I used example input files to submit the job on the DiffDock-L webserver and to run EquiBind and DiffDock-L programs on my Linux computer, and additionally, I collected 10 very new data samples to run EquiBind and DiffDock-L programs and computed RMSD (Root Mean Square Deviation) values, among of which PDB (Protein Data Bank) entry 8tgk (VMAT1 dimer and YHR reserpine) was chosen to do result visualization.

Method

For theoretical mechanism investigation

After doing literature survey [10-15], watching the authors' lecture video related to these tools, reading the programming source code (Table 2), I drew schematic diagrams and tried to write easily understandable description to illustrate the main mechanism of these 4 tools: EquiDock, EquiBind, DiffDock, DiffDock-L. Because DiffDock-L is an updated version of DiffDock, and there is only one Github code repository for maintaining DiffDock, since March of 2024, the default programming source code on that repository is DiffDock-L, so it is easy to find the source code of DiffDock-L but not the original DiffDock. In fact, I have not read the source code of original DiffDock.

Table 2. Online materials about 4 recent deep learning based molecular tools

Software	Lecture video URL	Programming source code URL
EquiDock	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=706KjyR-wyQ	https://github.com/octavian-ganea/equidock_public
EquiBind	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JAvh9e6XEGM	https://github.com/HannesStark/EquiBind
DiffDock	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gAmTGw601dA	https://github.com/gcorso/DiffDock
DiffDock-L	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UPh9pD-BSks	https://github.com/gcorso/DiffDock

For computational practice exploration

Among the 4 investigated tools, only DiffDock-L offers the online web-server. All of these 4 tools have Linux packages. I only did computational practice for 2 tools: EquiBind and DiffDock-L, and the reasons are below. EquiDock does not have command line interface. And if I want to run EquiDock for my specified input data, I have to modify the programming source code file. So, it is not convenient to run EquiDock. And the installation might be problematic. As for DiffDock, it is an old version software on the author Corso's Github website. By default, the current Github website contains the new version software DiffDock-L. To find and install the old version software DiffDock probably would be a laborious task. And I believe the new version software DiffDock-L should outperform the original DiffDock. Lastly, I describe the information of the hardware as below. For locally running EquiBind and DiffDock-L, I used my Linux laptop computer Dell XPS13. The information of CPU was Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-10710U CPU @ 1.10GHz, 6 cores and 2 threads per core, so totally 12 threads. No GPU. The size of memory is 16 GB.

Submit the job on DiffDock-L web-server

I inputted the example 6w70.pdb file(containing 1 chain of the original dimer protein) and 6w70_ligand.sdf file(containing 1 ligand structure) offered by the DiffDock-L web-server (<https://huggingface.co/spaces/reginabarzilaygroup/DiffDock-Web>), used the default parameters, then submitted the computational job. The running time was about 1 minute. Then I downloaded the output files, and used Chimera software on my Windows computer to do visualization of the predicted “rank1_confidence-0.79.sdf” file and official PDB entry 6w70 complex.

Locally run EquiBind and DiffDock-L for example input files

For downloaded DiffDock-L package, example input files “1a0q_protein_processed.pdb” and “1a0q_ligand.sdf file” were offered. However, for EquiBind, there was no example input file. Therefore, firstly I ran DiffDock-L on the offered example input files, then I ran EquiBind on the same input files. The Linux command for DiffDock-L was “python -m inference --config default_inference_args.yaml --protein_ligand_csv data/protein_ligand_example.csv --out_dir results/user_predictions_small”, and for EquiBind was “python inference.py --config=configs_clean/inference.yml”. I used the default parameters for both tools, separately. The running time of EquiBind and DiffDock-L for 1 sample were about 4 seconds and 7 minutes, separately. Then I used Chimera software on my Windows computer to do visualization of the EquiBind predicted ligand result file, DiffDock predicted rank1 ligand result file and official PDB entry 1a0q complex.

Locally run EquiBind and DiffDock-L for collected 10 new data samples

Collect 10 new data samples

Since the latest DiffDock-L was released on 2024-02-28, in order to let the new data samples have no chance of being in the training dataset for DiffDock-L and EquiBind, I went to the PDB website searching engine and set the search condition as the release date from 2024-03-02 to 2024-12-31. And I selected the organism(species) limited to human or mouse, typed in the keyword “drug”. Then I got a list of hundreds of protein/complex structures. Next, I picked 10 protein-ligand complexes and downloaded the PDB files. These 10 PDB entries were 8r4v, 8r99, 8tgk, 8tpv, 8uh3, 8vxu, 8xv2, 8xv5, 8xv9, 8y6h. I used Chimera software to prepare separate protein structure pdb file by deleting

all ligands in the complex. On the other hand, I download the ligand sdf files directly from corresponding PDB-code PDB website.

To verify that the downloaded ligand sdf file contains the bound structure of ligand in the complex, I took PDB entry 8tgk (a dimer protein VMAT1 with ligand YHR reserpine) for example and used Chimera software to do work below. I used command “open 8tgk” in Chimera software, then colored green on the selected ligand YHR reserpine, next I opened the downloaded “8tgk_ligand.sdf” file, and I colored red on the selected 8tgk_ligand. Then I can see the downloaded “8tgk_ligand.sdf” file contains the same structure with ligand YHR reserpine in the complex, and “8tgk_ligand.sdf” file includes all hydrogen atoms.

Locally run EquiBind and DiffDock-L

I locally ran EquiBind and DiffDock-L on these 10 new data samples mentioned above. For DiffDock-L, the output predicted ligand file will have a confidence score corresponding to each rank ligand pose, but for EquiBind there is no such confidence score. Furthermore, I used Linux command tool obrms to calculate the symmetry-corrected RMSD (Root Mean Square of Deviation) between predicted ligand pose and the ligand structure I downloaded from PDB website. Then I made tables of RMSD value for EquiBind and DiffDock-L running on these 10 new data samples. For result visualization, I took PDB entry 8tgk for example and used Chimera software.

Result

Theoretical mechanism investigation

In this section, instead of describing every detail of the 4 recent deep learning-based molecular tools, I prefer to illustrate the main idea of the corresponding mechanism. Table 3 shows an overview of the mechanism of EquiDock, EquiBind, DiffDock and DiffDock-L.

Table 3. Mechanism summary of 4 recent deep learning based molecular tools

Software	Docking type	Mechanism summary	Release date
EquiDock	Rigid protein-protein blind docking	Use attention mechanism to find key-points of ligand and receptor, then compute the rotation and translation matrixes to overlap these two sets of key-points.	2021/11/15
EquiBind	Flexible small molecule-protein blind docking	Find the binding position and ligand orientation based on the mechanism of EquiDock, but use normal geometry optimization to transform the input ligand to get chemically reasonable conformation.	2022/02/07
DiffDock	Flexible small molecule-protein blind docking	In training stage, artificially “diffuse” the true bound ligand to unbound state, then use reverse diffusion process to turn back to the bound state, and in inference stage, apply corresponding reverse diffusion process for the input ligand similar to the training data.	2022/10/04
DiffDock-L	Flexible small molecule-protein blind docking	By scaling law, increase the size of training dataset and the number of diffusion model’s parameters of the original DiffDock, and add inference tuning.	2024/02/28

EquiDock and EquiBind

In a very simplified way, I show the key idea of EquiDock and EquiBind in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The key ideas of EquiDock and EquiBind

Note: sub-figure C is partially adapted from the paper of Hannes Stark et al. in 2022 [7].

EquiDock is for rigid protein-protein blind docking. In training stage, the program uses attention mechanism to find K key-points of ligand protein and K key-points of receptor protein, then computes the rotational matrix and translational vector to make these two sets of key-points overlapped as much as possible. And then the program applies the same rotational matrix and translational vector on the whole original ligand protein, thus the final binding ligand protein can be obtained. In inference stage, the program applies corresponding rotational matrix and translational vector for the input ligand protein and receptor protein similar to the training data. There is no changing of the conformation for ligand protein and receptor protein.

EquiBind is for flexible small molecule-protein blind docking, and is based on EquiDock. Besides finding the binding pocket, the program also fine-tunes the conformation of the small molecule, to have high quality of compatibility with the superimposition of key-points. In this way, the docking result can be improved further.

For EquiBind, the original output of the neural network is ligand structure Z , it contains the information of the best binding mode. But it is not necessarily chemically reasonable. Thus, the program constructs the conformer C , which is generated by directly changing torsion angles of input ligand X , and makes C most similar to Z in the aspect of having the most similar torsion angles. Thus, conformer C can both satisfy the condition of being chemically reasonable and being fit for binding mode.

DiffDock and DiffDock-L

The basic idea of DiffDock and DiffDock-L is utilizing the diffusion generative model to simulate the binding and unbinding moments of the ligand molecule (Figure 3). DiffDock-L is just an updated version of DiffDock, and the foundational mechanism is still the diffusion generative model.

Figure 3. The key idea of DiffDock

Note: this figure is made up by the several snapshots of Hannes Stärk's lecture video on <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gAmTGw601dA>

The intuitive understanding of DiffDock model is below. In training stage, the program artificially applies the forward “diffusion force” to the original true ligand in bound state, let the ligand gradually become in some unbound states. Then the neural network model is encouraged to generate a series of transformation to the diffused ligands. Through this reverse diffusion process, the diffused ligands can approximately turn back to the bound state. By training on a large dataset, the neural network model can “memorize” the diffused ligand poses at the end of the forward diffusion process. In inference stage, when the model encounters some similar ligand in unbound state and corresponding protein, the model may have the ability to turn the ligand roughly to the bound state.

The motivation of updating DiffDock to DiffDock-L is that, the authors found that when using the original DiffDock to predict on some unseen types of complexes, the prediction accuracy was not so good. And the major changes in DiffDock-L are below. (1) Increase the size of the training dataset by introducing another dataset BindingMOAD and (2) introducing van der Mers synthetic protein-side chain ligand complex data. (3) Increase the number of diffusion model's parameters from 20 million to 30 million. (4) Add inference tuning. Therefore, the “L” in DiffDock-L means larger size of training dataset and larger number of model's parameters.

Computational practice exploration

Submit the job on DiffDock-L web-server

The result of DiffDock-L web-server for PDB entry 6w70's ligand and protein is below.

A. Snapshot of output file folder of DiffDock-L web-server

6w70.pdb	2024/5/20 1:23	PDB 文件	256 KB
rank1.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank1_confidence-0.79.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank2_confidence-1.06.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank3_confidence-1.14.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank4_confidence-1.16.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank5_confidence-1.17.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank6_confidence-1.24.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank7_confidence-1.27.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank8_confidence-2.56.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank9_confidence-2.67.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB
rank10_confidence-2.74.sdf	2024/5/20 1:23	SDF 文件	4 KB

B. Visualization of DiffDock-L web-server rank1 prediction result

Figure 4. Result of DiffDock-L web-server for PDB entry 6w70's ligand and protein

For sub-figure B, two green circles indicate the positions of the true ligands GG2 in the complex. Two true ligands GG2 are with green outline. Predicted ligand of "rank1_confidence-0.79.sdf" file is with blue color. On the right is a close-up picture from another perspective.

The predicted ligand of "rank1_confidence-0.79.sdf" file was located roughly in the protein binding pocket. Although the predicted ligand pose did not perfectly superimpose with the true ligand, the main axes of them seem to be close to each other.

Locally run EquiBind and DiffDock-L for example input files

I ran EquiBind and DiffDock-L on my Linux computer for example input files “1a0q_protein_processed.pdb” and “1a0q_ligand.sdf file” offered by DiffDock-L package. EquiBind only produced 1 predicted binding ligand pose file, while DiffDock-L produced 10 predicted binding ligand poses files with confidence values.

Figure 5. Prediction results of EquiBind and DiffDock-L for PDB entry 1a0q

On the left, the two pictures are both 1a0q complex from PDB website containing true protein and true ligand. On the right, the EquiBind predicted ligand pose and DiffDock-L predicted rank1 ligand pose (confidence value 0.16) were added with blue color, separately. Red boxes indicate the region about true ligand or predicted ligand.

In Figure 5, both of predicted ligands of EquiBind and DiffDock-L rank1 were located in the binding pocket of the receptor protein. However, for DiffDock-L rank1, the predicted ligand was superimposed very well with the true ligand structure, while the superimposition for EquiBind was bad. Thus, by rough comparison, the accuracy of predicted ligand pose of DiffDock-L rank1 was apparently higher than EquiBind.

Locally run EquiBind and DiffDock-L for collected 10 new data samples

As we know, deep learning methods are data driven or data dependent. If we want to find some meaningful insights for the future study, then trying such deep learning methods on the very new data seems a good exploration way. Therefore, I carefully collected 10 new ligand-protein complexes released after March 1 of 2024 from PDB website. Then I used the simplest procedure (see the right part of Figure 1) to do molecular docking, by locally running EquiBind and DiffDock-L on these 10

new data samples. Further, I calculated symmetry-corrected RMSD (Root Mean Square of Deviation) values between the true ligands and the predicted ligand poses.

In the main content of this report, I choose PDB entry 8tgk complex to show the visualization result (Figure 6). In this complex, the protein is VMAT1(Vesicular Mono-Amine Transporter 1, a dimer with two chains), and the ligand is YHR reserpine (an antihypertensive drug). The attractive point of this complex is that VMATs are highly related to neurological, endocrinal and immunological functions in human. As for the remaining results of other complexes, they can be found in the supplementary material attached to this report.

Figure 6. Prediction results of EquiBind and DiffDock-L for PDB entry 8tgk

Red boxes indicate the positions of predicted ligand poses. In sub-figure B, on the left are close-up pictures of the predicted rank1 ligand pose by DiffDock-L from two perspectives, in the middle and on the right are the pictures containing rank1 to rank10 ligand poses separately, among which rank1 ligand pose is colored yellow and the remaining ligand poses are colored purple.

Table 4. RMSD and Confidence Score for prediction results of EquiBind and DiffDock-L on PDB entry 8tgk

Bold fonts indicate the predicted ligand poses located in Chain B and corresponding RMSD values.

RMSD calculation ID	Symmetry corrected RMSD(Å)	Located in which chain	Docking method	Pose rank	Confidence Score
8tgk_EquiBind_01	45.45	A	EquiBind		
8tgk_DiffDock_01	2.95	B	DiffDock-L	1	-1.36
8tgk_DiffDock_02	11.10	B	DiffDock-L	2	-1.73
8tgk_DiffDock_03	48.41	A	DiffDock-L	3	-2.5
8tgk_DiffDock_04	46.05	A	DiffDock-L	4	-2.78
8tgk_DiffDock_05	10.12	B	DiffDock-L	5	-3.03
8tgk_DiffDock_06	45.14	A	DiffDock-L	6	-3.75
8tgk_DiffDock_07	47.12	A	DiffDock-L	7	-3.94
8tgk_DiffDock_08	45.11	A	DiffDock-L	8	-4.10
8tgk_DiffDock_09	45.05	A	DiffDock-L	9	-4.13
8tgk_DiffDock_10	45.02	A	DiffDock-L	10	-4.52

Firstly, we can see from Figure 6, in the true 8tgk complex structure, there was only one ligand YHR reserpine molecule and it was located in the Chain B of the dimer protein VMAT1. However, the single EquiBind predicted ligand pose was located in the Chain A rather than Chain B, and the corresponding RMSD value (Table 4) was very large (45.45 Å). This is probably because EquiBind can only read the first chain of the receptor protein, and by default ignores all the remaining chains in the protein pdb file. By contrast, DiffDock-L can output 10 predicted ligand poses, among which 3 ligand poses were located in the Chain B and 7 were in the Chain A. Apparently, the DiffDock-L predicted rank1 ligand pose was relatively closer to the true ligand, either according to the RMSD value (2.95 Å) or the visualization of the structure. Thus, DiffDock-L can produce more accurate binding ligand poses on the very top rank results, and also can offer some possible binding ligand poses in the other similar chain of the dimer protein.

Discussion

In this discussion section, I will mainly focus on the advantage and disadvantage of EquiBind and DiffDock-L (Table 5).

Table 5. Advantage and disadvantage of EquiBind and DiffDock-L

Software	Advantage	Disadvantage
EquiBind	Fast. Blind docking.	Not very accurate. Data dependent. Cannot handle multi-mer protein.
DiffDock-L	Simple operation. Can handle multi-mer protein and produce multiple possible ligand poses. Blind docking.	Data dependent. Slow. Program running failed for some input data.

EquiBind

The first impression of using EquiBind to me was that the program running was super fast.

EquiBind's prediction for a pair of ligand and protein only took 4 seconds on my Linux laptop computer, while DiffDock-L took about 7 minutes. And the running time of traditional molecular docking tool AutoDock Vina may be in between EquiBind and DiffDock-L. Nevertheless, usually we need to set the small binding pocket region before running Vina to decrease the searching space, thus the comparison of running time cannot be so straight forward. Next, we can get the second advantage of EquiBind is that it performs blind docking, which means this tool need less operation of human, and we do not need to set many parameters of the program. This advantage is also true for DiffDock-L.

On the other side, the largest problem of EquiBind is the lower accuracy, especially for the predicted ligand orientation and conformation. The authors of DiffDock once provided their opinion about EquiBind, which I think it did make some sense. EquiBind only produces one predicted ligand pose, and it is an average result or overall distance-smallest result for training dataset. But the true ligand has a specific orientation and conformation. So, it is hard for EquiBind to predict a specific perfect ligand pose. Instead, DiffDock tries to reversely diffuse the input unbound ligand into a relatively specific bound state in the training dataset, and it outputs 10 predicted ligand poses, each one has its own probability of being a specific ligand pose in bound state. So, some of these ligand poses can be closer to the true ligand in bound state.

Although the problem of being data dependent for EquiBind is not obvious (because at the first stage EquiBind's accuracy is not good, so nobody tests it too much on other data), I think it does exist since it is a machine learning model trained on a dataset, and it is nearly impossible to include all (classes of) data in that dataset. In fact, we can see in Figure 6.A of prediction results of EquiBind on new data sample PDB entry 8tgk, even though the true ligand and the predicted ligand were in two chains of the dimer protein, we still can intuitively feel that the true ligand was vertical while the predicted ligand was horizontal. Thus, we can guess that the accuracy of EquiBind on new data will be worse. Besides, another disadvantage of EquiBind is that it cannot handle multi-mer protein.

DiffDock-L

As for the disadvantage of DiffDock-L, firstly, it has the problem of being data dependent too (Figure 5 and Figure 6). But this can be alleviated by introducing the new data into the training dataset under the scaling law about diffusion generative model. And I think the RMSD value 2.95Å of predicted rank1 ligand pose on new data sample in Table 4 is not too bad. However, program running speed was slow and failed for some input data samples, which really bothered me. The running time of DiffDock-L for 10 new data samples was 76 minutes, while of EquiBind was less than 1 minute! And DiffDock-L failed for running on 3 samples, but EquiBind succeeded for all 10 samples.

The advantageous aspects of DiffDock-L are as below. First of all, the operation about DiffDock-L was really simple. At the very beginning stage, we can use the DiffDock-L web-server to submit the computational job without installing any Linux package. And in my experience, the preparation work for input files was easy. I did not need to remove any polypeptide chain of the dimer protein. Basically, I just removed the ligand in the complex pdb file. More importantly and meaningfully, DiffDock-L can produce multiple possible ligand poses located in several chains of multi-mer protein, which gave me the impression that DiffDock-L was more intelligent than other molecular docking tools.

Conclusion

Since the end of 2021, with the one of the earliest deep learning-based molecular docking tool EquiDock released, other software utilizing neural network model gradually have come out, such as EquiBind, DiffDock and DiffDock-L. It is beneficial for computational biologists and biomedical researchers to notice these new tools and have intuition understanding of their mechanism. Briefly speaking, EquiDock uses attention mechanism to find key-points, EquiBind introduces conformation fine-tuning for small molecule ligand, DiffDock performs forward and reverse diffusion processes, DiffDock-L applies the scaling law to improve accuracy. And for the practical prediction, DiffDock-L seems to be most accurate and useful among them. Anyway, these deep learning tools heavily rely on the data which have been used to train the model. When predicting binding mode on very new protein or ligand structures, we should not believe that the results would be precise. So far, we have to say, even in the best performance cases, the prediction result of DiffDock-L just can be considered roughly acceptable, and we need more effort to do improvement in the future exploration.

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Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. RMSD for prediction results of EquiBind on the 10 new data samples released on PDB website

RMSD calculation ID	Symmetry corrected RMSD(Å)
8r4v_EquiBind_01	38.65
8r99_EquiBind_01	2.91
8tgk_EquiBind_01	45.45
8tpv_EquiBind_01	20.46
8uh3_EquiBind_01	53.66
8vxu_EquiBind_01	21.66
8xv2_EquiBind_01	10.57
8xv5_EquiBind_01	9.91
8xv9_EquiBind_01	10.43
8y6h_EquiBind_01	7.83

Supplementary Table 2. RMSD and Confidence Score for prediction results of DiffDock-L on the 7 new data samples released on PDB website

Originally, there were 10 data samples as input for DiffDock-L, but 3 failed for programming running, thus there were only 7 had output results.

RMSD calculation ID	Symmetry corrected RMSD(Å)	Pose rank	Confidence score
8r99_DiffDock_01	2.26	1	-1.05
8r99_DiffDock_02	2.56	2	-1.08
8r99_DiffDock_03	2.52	3	-1.14
8r99_DiffDock_04	2.60	4	-1.15
8r99_DiffDock_05	2.58	5	-1.2
8r99_DiffDock_06	2.59	6	-1.2
8r99_DiffDock_07	2.47	7	-1.2
8r99_DiffDock_08	2.57	8	-1.24
8r99_DiffDock_09	2.53	9	-1.25
8r99_DiffDock_10	2.10	10	-1.26
8tgk_DiffDock_01	2.95	1	-1.36
8tgk_DiffDock_02	11.10	2	-1.73
8tgk_DiffDock_03	48.41	3	-2.5
8tgk_DiffDock_04	46.05	4	-2.78
8tgk_DiffDock_05	10.12	5	-3.03
8tgk_DiffDock_06	45.14	6	-3.75
8tgk_DiffDock_07	47.12	7	-3.94
8tgk_DiffDock_08	45.11	8	-4.1
8tgk_DiffDock_09	45.05	9	-4.13
8tgk_DiffDock_10	45.02	10	-4.52
8tpv_DiffDock_01	56.60	1	-0.73
8tpv_DiffDock_02	56.61	2	-0.8
8tpv_DiffDock_03	46.46	3	-0.82

8tpv_DiffDock_04	6.32	4	-0.94
8tpv_DiffDock_05	56.79	5	-0.95
8tpv_DiffDock_06	46.63	6	-1.01
8tpv_DiffDock_07	33.15	7	-1.08
8tpv_DiffDock_08	57.23	8	-1.33
8tpv_DiffDock_09	57.33	9	-1.34
8tpv_DiffDock_10	6.39	10	-1.43
8uh3_DiffDock_01	4.31	1	-0.09
8uh3_DiffDock_02	4.31	2	-0.1
8uh3_DiffDock_03	4.34	3	-0.15
8uh3_DiffDock_04	2.69	4	-0.24
8uh3_DiffDock_05	2.70	5	-0.26
8uh3_DiffDock_06	2.77	6	-0.27
8uh3_DiffDock_07	2.75	7	-0.28
8uh3_DiffDock_08	2.74	8	-0.32
8uh3_DiffDock_09	58.09	9	-1.14
8uh3_DiffDock_10	61.35	10	-5.29
8xv2_DiffDock_01	16.07	1	-0.83
8xv2_DiffDock_02	9.23	2	-1.53
8xv2_DiffDock_03	8.99	3	-1.63
8xv2_DiffDock_04	9.23	4	-1.8
8xv2_DiffDock_05	9.45	5	-1.82
8xv2_DiffDock_06	8.04	6	-1.91
8xv2_DiffDock_07	9.29	7	-1.99
8xv2_DiffDock_08	11.01	8	-2.34
8xv2_DiffDock_09	14.60	9	-2.89
8xv2_DiffDock_10	16.08	10	-4.72
8xv5_DiffDock_01	19.76	1	-0.59
8xv5_DiffDock_02	18.44	2	-0.7
8xv5_DiffDock_03	17.50	3	-0.82
8xv5_DiffDock_04	16.57	4	-1.02
8xv5_DiffDock_05	16.89	5	-1.27
8xv5_DiffDock_06	15.87	6	-1.62
8xv5_DiffDock_07	7.15	7	-1.63
8xv5_DiffDock_08	17.04	8	-1.81
8xv5_DiffDock_09	21.00	9	-2
8xv5_DiffDock_10	10.54	10	-2.35
8xv9_DiffDock_01	18.39	1	-1.2
8xv9_DiffDock_02	9.43	2	-1.46
8xv9_DiffDock_03	10.44	3	-1.58
8xv9_DiffDock_04	10.57	4	-1.61
8xv9_DiffDock_05	10.50	5	-1.83
8xv9_DiffDock_06	11.37	6	-2.19
8xv9_DiffDock_07	11.06	7	-2.22
8xv9_DiffDock_08	10.53	8	-2.27
8xv9_DiffDock_09	12.20	9	-2.42
8xv9_DiffDock_10	9.87	10	-2.69
